

A COMPARISON OF THE FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF

WOVEN AND NON-WOVEN CFRP LAMINATES

P.T.Curtis and B.B.Moore

Materials and Structures Dept.
Royal Aircraft Establishment
Farnborough, Hants.
UK.

SUMMARY

Static and fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature on CFRP laminates with five lay-ups, of both woven and non-woven CFRP. S-N diagrams were produced for zero-tension fatigue loading. Damage development was monitored by optical microscopy, ultrasonic C-scanning, video recording and infra-red thermography.

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics made with woven fabric rather than non-woven material, had significantly poorer tensile static and fatigue performance than non-woven material, due to distortion of the load carrying 0° fibres. However, when woven fabric was oriented at 45° to the load direction, the tensile static and fatigue performance was slightly better than in non-woven $\pm 45^\circ$ material. Replacing just the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of a $(\pm 45, 0)$ laminate with woven fabric had little effect on the tensile static or fatigue strength.

In non-woven material, notched coupons under fatigue loading did not show the notch sensitivity that was so significant under static loading. However in woven material, because of the additional fatigue degradation processes associated with tow crossover points in the weave, holed coupons never quite achieved notch insensitivity in fatigue.

Copyright C Controller HMSO London (1985)

Paper presented at ICCM V, San Diego, 1985.

Introduction

Increasing use is being made of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) in the aerospace industry because of their combination of high stiffness and high strength with low density and potentially low unit cost. In addition, the fatigue performance of CFRP has been shown to be very good, being superior to many other materials including metals (1).

At present, most carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin laminates are made from non-woven unidirectional prepregged sheets. This material is beginning to find extensive use in military aerospace applications, initially in class 2 structures but more recently in class 1 structures as in the McDonnell Douglas AV8B and F-18 aircraft (2,3).

Recently, good quality woven carbon fibre cloth has been obtainable, prepreg manufacturers now being able to supply woven carbon fibre preregs in the form familiar to users of the non-woven material. Many types of weave are available such as, plain, twill and satin, but work on GRP and early work with woven CFRP (4) has shown that weaves with less fibre distortion, such as satin weaves (in particular five or eight shaft satin weaves for CFRP), result in smaller reductions in mechanical properties.

The main reasons for the use of woven fabric are the ease of handling which lends itself to automation and consequent reductions in labour, the ability of fabric to conform to complex shapes and the fabric has more isotropic in-plane properties compared with unidirectional material. In addition, woven CFRP can result in better containment of impact damage and improved residual properties after impact compared with non-woven material (5,6).

At present there is a significant gap in our knowledge of the behaviour of composites made with carbon fibre fabric, particularly compared with non-woven material. In this report the findings of a programme comparing the fatigue response of laminates fabricated from woven and non-woven CFRP are presented. Since previous work had shown that laminates with only the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers replaced by woven fabric showed superior impact performance to non-woven laminates (5,6), these were also included for study in this programme of work. The full S-N behaviour of five lay-ups has been characterised in tensile loading in the plain and notched conditions, and damage development studied using optical microscopy, ultrasonic C-scanning and infra-red thermography.

Experimental Details

Laminates were moulded from both woven and non-woven pre-impregnated sheets of high strength Toray T300 carbon fibres in Ciba-Geigy BSL914C epoxy resin. The carbon fibre fabric was a balanced five shaft satin weave, woven with 3000 filament tows of the same fibre type used in the non-woven material, but including a fine tracer tow of Kevlar 49 fibres

every 50mm. In this weave about 80% of the fibres in one direction lie on one side of the cloth and correspondingly about 80% of the fibres lie at right angles on the other side of the cloth. Since one prepreg sheet of woven material was approximately twice as thick (0.267mm) as a ply of non-woven material (0.125mm), each sheet of cloth was thus similar to two plies of non-woven unidirectional prepreg stacked at 90° to each other as in a (0,90) or (+/-45) lay-up.

Symmetrical woven and non-woven laminates with equivalent stacking sequences were made up, each approximately 1mm thick, with five types of lay-up as listed below.

- A. {0,90,90,0}s
- B. {+/-45,-/+45}s
- C. {+/-45,0,90}s
- D. {0,90,+/-45}s
- E. {+/-45,0}2s

The woven prepreg was stacked so that the dominant fibre direction on each face of the cloth corresponded with the appropriate direction in the non-woven stacking sequence. In (0,90,+/-45) laminates with 50% 0°/90° layers and 50% +/-45° layers the stacking sequence was varied so that either the +/-45° layers or the 0°/90° layers were on the laminate surface. In addition, (+/-45,0) laminates (lay-up E) were made from both non-woven material and from a mixture of woven and non-woven plies; the 0° layers were of non-woven material and the +/-45° layers were of woven material.

The laminates were cured in an autoclave to 170°C and postcured for four hours at 190°C. All the laminates with woven carbon fibre fabric were 12-17% thicker than the equivalent non-woven laminates. Approximately 10% of this difference in thickness was due to the lower volume fraction of the woven carbon fibre laminates and the remainder was due to the fabric containing more fibre by weight than two non-woven plies. The laminates were stored in a controlled environment at 23°C and 65% relative humidity for at least three months prior to testing. The moisture content after this time was approximately 1%.

Tests were carried out on coupons 250mm long, with the warp fibres (along the length of the fabric) parallel to the 0° load direction in the 0°/90° woven layers (previous work had shown no significant difference between warp and weft properties (5)). Coupons 250mm long and 20mm wide were cut from the laminates, except for lay-up B (+/-45) for which coupons 40mm wide were used to obtain sufficient loads to preserve fatigue machine controlability. Notched coupons each contained a central 4mm diameter hole. Etched aluminium alloy end plates were bonded to the abraded ends of all coupons.

Static tests and constant amplitude fatigue tests were performed using servo-hydraulic fatigue machines in zero-tension (P+/-P) loading. Static tests were performed in position control at a ram speed of between 1.5mm/min and 2.5mm/min and fatigue tests in load control at frequencies of between 5 and 20 Hz depending on the sensitivity of the lay-up to hysteresis heating. Ultrasonic C-scan and optical microscopy

were used to study the development of damage during fatigue loading. Some coupons had their edges polished for examination by optical microscopy. Tests were then performed at the fatigue stress level that gave a mean lifetime of 100,000 cycles, and were stopped after 1000, 10000 and 50000 cycles for assessment of the damage state of the coupons. Damage development during the tests was also studied using an optical video camera and an infra-red thermography system.

Results

Static tests

The results of the static tests on all lay-ups, for tensile loading of both plain and holed coupons, woven and non-woven, are given in tables 1 to 5. In all lay-ups the plain coupons, both woven and non-woven, failed at random along their lengths, but holed coupons all failed through the holes.

Table I. Static Tests on Lay-up A

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>Type</u>	<u>Loading</u>	<u>Failure stress MPa</u>
WUA-3	Non-woven plain	Tension	697
WUA-37	731
WUA-9	Non-woven holed	..	586
WUA-31	605
WXA-3	Woven plain	Tension	571
WXA-37	623
WXA-9	Woven holed	..	425
WXA-31	377

Table II. Static Tests on Lay-up B

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>type</u>	<u>Loading</u>	<u>Failure stress MPa.</u>
WUB-2	Non-woven plain	Tension	174
WUB-19	205
WUB-3	Non-woven holed	..	208
WUB-20	205
WXB-2	Woven plain	Tension	174
WXB-19	210
WXB-3	Woven holed	..	216
WXB-20	214

Table III. Static Tests on Lay-up C

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>type</u>	<u>Loading</u>	<u>Failure stress MPa.</u>
WUC-3	Non-woven plain	Tension	441
WUC-37	476
WUC-9	Non-woven holed	..	288
WUC-31	363
WXC-3	Woven plain	Tension	422
WXC-37	442
WXC-9	Woven holed	..	304
WXC-31	306

Table IV. Static Tests on Lay-up D

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>type</u>	<u>Loading</u>	<u>Failure stress MPa.</u>
WUD-3	Non-woven plain	Tension	546
WUD-37	584
WUD-9	Non-woven holed	..	428
WUD-31	410
WXD-3	Woven plain	Tension	434
WXD-37	429
WXD-9	Woven holed	..	336
WXD-31	339

Table V. Static Tests on Lay-up E

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>Type</u>	<u>Loading</u>	<u>Failure stress MPa</u>
WUE-3	Non-woven plain	Tension	799
WUE-37	825
WUE-9	Non-woven holed	..	590
WUE-31	603
WXE-3	Mixed-woven plain	Tension	800
WXE-37	809
WXE-9	Mixed-woven holed	..	565
WXE-31	542

Zero-tension Fatigue

Lay-up A (0,90). Results of the fatigue tests are plotted as peak stress versus log.life (S-N plot) in fig.1. Stresses are plotted on a net area basis, as they are throughout this report. Coupons failed at random positions along their lengths, except for the holed coupons which all failed through the holes. Plain non-woven coupons developed extensive longitudinal splits at their edges in the 0 degree plies which became more extensive with increasing numbers of cycles. Holed non-woven coupons also showed evidence of longitudinal splitting of the surface plies at a tangent to the hole edges. Although some longitudinal splitting was also observed at the edges of the woven coupons, it was far less extensive and never developed to the same degree as in the non-woven coupons.

Optical microscopy of plain coupons revealed longitudinal edge cracks along the edges of the non-woven coupons after 1000 cycles at the stress level that gave a mean life of 100000 cycles, but no similar damage was observed in the woven coupons. Both woven and non-woven coupons developed extensive transverse cracks across the 90° layers early in the tests and these tended to initiate delamination after large numbers of fatigue cycles. Delamination was more noticeable in the non-woven material.

The ultrasonic C-scans revealed an overall lightening with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles, for both woven and non-woven coupons, although the effect was more marked in the woven coupons (fig.2) in which light areas developed at the tow crossover points in the weave. C-scans of the holed non-woven coupons showed evidence of damage development around the holes, becoming quite extensive after large numbers of cycles,

Figure 1 - S-N curves for coupons with lay-up A (0,90).
 (↪ denotes a run out).

Figure 2 - Ultrasonic C-scans of holed woven coupons with lay-up A, after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

Figure 3 - Ultrasonic C-scans of holed non-woven coupons with lay-up A, after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

spreading up to half the length of the coupons (fig.3). The holed woven coupons behaved similarly, except that the damage was less extensive (fig.2).

Lay-up B. Results of the fatigue tests on lay-up B are plotted as peak stress versus log.life (S-N plot) in fig.4. It is clear that in these S-N curves the percentage loss of static strength with increasing fatigue lifetime was greater than in the $0,90$ laminates. All four curves were similar, except that the woven $\pm 45^\circ$ material, both plain and holed, gave longer lifetimes at the lower fatigue stresses. All holed coupons failed through the holes, but plain non-woven coupons showed a tendency to fail 2cm to 3cm from either end, although several failures did occur away from the ends.

Optical microscopy of plain coupon edges during testing at the stress level that gave a mean life of 100000 cycles revealed edge delamination cracking in non-woven coupons after 1000 cycles as well as translaminar cracking. This became more extensive after 10000 and 50000 cycles, with delamination being particularly noticeable, failure occurring by the linking of delamination and translaminar cracks. All woven coupons, in particular the $\pm 45^\circ$ coupons, showed poor fibre distribution compared with non-woven material. Fibres were packed closely together in the tows with large resin rich regions between. After 1000 cycles of fatigue loading, cracks had developed around several of the fibre tows, these becoming more extensive by 10000 and 50000 cycles with the development of translaminar cracks (fig.5). There was no extensive delamination spanning long sections of the gauge length as in the non-woven material.

Figure 4 - S-N curves for coupons with lay-up B (+/-45).
 (L denotes run-outs).

Figure 5 - Optical micrographs of woven coupons with lay-up B after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

Failure occurred by the linking of translaminar cracks and damage around fibre tows.

Ultrasonic C-scanning revealed the development of damage zones close to the grips in the plain non-woven coupons. Failure frequently occurred at one of these sites. The effect was not observed in the holed non-woven coupons, which showed instead the development of a damage zone around the holes leading to subsequent failure through the holes. There was no overall lightening of the C-scans with increasing numbers of cycles as observed in the ($0,90$) coupons. The woven coupons did, however, exhibit a noticeable lightening of the C-scans with increasing numbers of cycles (fig.6). As in the plain non-woven coupons there was evidence of the development of damage zones close to the ends, but damage also developed more generally, particularly at $+45$ and -45 degrees to the coupon axis, and failure occurred away from the ends. The holed woven coupons also showed similar behaviour (fig.6), but damage was also observed around the holes, this taking the form of a cross shape at ± 45 degrees, failure then occurring along one of the arms of the cross.

Lay-up C. Results of the fatigue tests are plotted as net peak stress versus log.life (S-N plot) in fig.7. Plain coupons all failed at random positions along their lengths but holed coupons all failed through the holes. Longitudinal edge cracking was visible in some coupons, mainly in the plain non-woven coupons. Woven coupons did develop edge cracks but at greater lifetimes than the non-woven coupons.

Optical microscopy of plain non-woven coupons revealed tranverse 90 layer cracks initiated early in the test, probably during the first few loading cycles. These initiated edge cracking between the 0 and 90 layers at higher numbers of cycles.

Optical microscopy of the woven coupons revealed slightly different behaviour (fig.8). Transverse cracks formed across individual 90 tows early in the tests followed by edge cracks in the 90 tows and at $0/90$ interfaces. In addition, because of the woven nature of the plies, the 90 tows were often adjacent to the ± 45 layers and edge cracking was also observed at these interfaces. Cracking was especially apparent in the resin rich regions between the woven tows. Close to failure, fractured 0 fibres or tows were also observed.

Ultrasonic C-scanning of non-woven coupons revealed light lines across the coupons after 1000 cycles, probably caused by short lengths of delamination at the ends of transverse cracks (fig.9). At increased numbers of cycles a lightening of the edges was observed which spread across the coupon width towards the middle. Holed coupons showed less edge whitening and no transverse lightening, but did exhibit lightening around the holes. This eventually linked up with the edge lightening and commenced spreading longitudinally along the coupons.

Ultrasonic C-scanning of plain woven coupons revealed an overall lightening with increasing numbers of cycles and the gradual development of lighter spots at the tow crossover points in the weave. A few tranverse light lines were observed

Figure 6 - Ultrasonic C-scans of a woven hole coupon with lay-up B after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

Figure 7 - S-N curves for coupons with lay-up C (+/-45, 0, 90). (L_p denotes run-outs and ↓ run-up failures).

Figure 8 - Optical micrographs of woven coupons with lay-up C after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles. a=1000, b=10000, c=50000 and d=150000.

Figure 9 - Ultrasonic C-scans of a non-woven coupon with lay-up C after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

as in the non-woven material, as well as edge lightening, although this was not as extensive as in the non-woven material. Holed woven coupons exhibited similar behaviour but less obvious than in the plain woven coupons. In addition, light areas developed around the holes and, as in the non-woven coupons, eventually linked up with the edge lightening.

Lay-up D. Results of the fatigue tests are plotted as net peak stress versus log.life (S-N plot) in fig.10. Plain coupons all failed at random positions along their lengths but holed coupons all failed through the holes. Longitudinal edge cracking was less obvious than in coupons with lay-up C.

Optical microscopy of plain non-woven coupons revealed tranverse 90° layer cracks, probably initiated during the first few loading cycles, which generated edge cracks in the 90° layers at higher numbers of cycles, but these were less extensive than in lay-up C. Delamination between layers was observed after large numbers of cycles.

Optical microscopy of the woven coupons revealed slightly different behaviour. Transverse cracks formed across individual 90° tows early in the tests as well as $0^\circ/90^\circ$ delamination between individual tows. Limited edge cracks developed in the 90° tows and at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces. After large numbers of cycles, delamination was visible and damage in the 90° plies became quite extensive, especially in resin rich regions between the tows.

Ultrasonic C-scanning of non-woven coupons revealed no tranverse lightening as seen in coupons from lay-up C. After 10,000 cycles some edge lightening was observed but by 100,000 cycles a more general lightening of the coupons was observed and close to the edge the lightening had extended almost across the full coupon widths in places. Holed coupons exhibited some edge lightening after large numbers of cycles but no tranverse lightening, although they did exhibit lightening around the holes. This eventually linked up with the edge lightening and commenced spreading longitudinally along the coupons.

Ultrasonic C-scanning of plain woven coupons revealed an overall lightening with increasing numbers of cycles and the gradual development of lighter spots at tow crossover points in the weave (fig.11), as in coupons from lay-up C, but no tranverse light lines. Edge lightening was apparent, but this was very limited and never extended more than 1 to 2 mm from the coupon edges. Holed coupons showed similar behaviour, but less obvious than in the plain woven coupons (fig.11). The light areas that developed around the holes, as in the non-woven coupons, eventually linked up with the edge lightening and spread longitudinally along the coupon edges but not above or below the hole.

Lay-up E. Results of the tensile fatigue tests are plotted as S-N curves in fig.12. All plain coupons failed at random positions along their lengths and holed non-woven coupons also failed away from the holes. Holed woven coupons failed through the holes at short lifetimes but those coupons surviving to long lifetimes failed away from the holes. Both woven and non-woven coupons showed evidence of edge splitting

Figure 10 - S-N curves for coupons with lay-up $D (0,90,+/-45)$.
 (\downarrow denotes run-up failures).

Figure 11 - Ultrasonic C-scans of a woven holed coupon with lay-up D after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

Figure 12 - S-N curves for coupons with lay-up E (+/-45,0). (↓ denotes run-up failures).

Figure 13 - Ultrasonic C-scans of a holed non-woven coupon with lay-up E after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

and delamination at long lifetimes.

Optical microscopy of plain woven and non-woven coupons revealed +/- 45 delamination and translaminal cracking after only 1000 cycles. This became more extensive after 10,000 and 100,000 cycles. Above 100,000 cycles there was evidence of fibre damage.

Ultrasonic C-scanning of plain non-woven coupons revealed little apart from a slight lightening after 1000 cycles and some evidence of damage growth around the coupon ends after large numbers of cycles. Holed non-woven coupons revealed damage around the holes after 10,000 cycles (fig.13) which grew longitudinally to a distance of several hole diameters after one million cycles. Eventually the damage reached the coupon ends and had also grown across the coupon width (fig.13).

Ultrasonic C-scanning of plain woven coupons revealed only the gradual lightening and development of light spots with increasing numbers of fatigue load cycles observed in the other woven laminates (fig.14). The holed woven coupons exhibited a similar effect to that observed in the non-woven coupons. Damage was observed around the hole after only 1000 cycles and grew longitudinally to a distance of several hole diameters after 100,000 cycles (fig.14). The damage did not extend quite as far as the grips but did grow across the coupon width.

Figure 14 - Ultrasonic C-scans of a holed mixed-woven coupon with lay-up E after increasing numbers of fatigue cycles.

Discussion

Static tests

The results of static tests on the $(0,90)$ laminates, given in table 1, revealed that the plain woven coupons were 16% weaker than the non-woven coupons. Part of this difference was due to the fibre volume fraction being approximately 10% lower than in the non-woven coupons, an inevitable consequence of the fibre tow distortion in the weave. The additional strength reduction was due to reduced material strength directly associated with the distortion of the fibre tows, indeed similar effects were observed in earlier work on $(0,90)$ laminates (5,6). Both woven and non-woven $(0,90)$ laminates were notch sensitive, the strength of the non-woven material falling by 17% in the presence of a 4mm hole and the woven material by 33%. This implies that the woven $(0,90)$ material was more notch sensitive than the non-woven material, an observation also made in previous work (5). This was due to the inhibition of stress relieving and energy absorbing mechanisms at the edge of the hole; in woven material longitudinal splitting at the hole would be restricted to the undistorted length of the weave and delamination would also be contained.

The woven (± 45) laminates were slightly stronger statically than the non-woven material (table 2), implying that the lower fibre volume fraction and greater fibre distortion had little effect on strength, although previous work (5) indicated that the failure strain was reduced. The increased load carrying capacity of the fibres in the woven fabric was probably due to the inhibition of in-plane shear deformation and delamination due to the woven and undulating nature of the fabric, which is also consistent with the reduced failure strain. All (± 45) lay-ups were effectively notch insensitive, a widely reported fact, and similar values of failure stress were obtained for woven and non-woven coupons with 4mm central holes.

Coupons with the $(\pm 45,0,90)$ lay-up (lay-up C) had lower tensile strengths than either the $(0,90)$ or $(0,\pm 45)$ lay-ups, a consequence of the smaller percentage of 0° load bearing fibres. The plain woven material was only 6% weaker than the non-woven material (table 3), a reduction in keeping with the lower fibre volume fraction, implying that the fibre distortion had no effect on the strength of the woven material. This disparity with the $(0,90)$ or $(0,90,\pm 45)$ lay-ups is difficult to explain but may be associated with anomalous scatter due to the small sample size. Both the woven and non-woven material with 4mm central holes lost 29% in strength compared with the plain material. The similar notch sensitivity in both materials is in contrast to the $(0,90)$ lay-up in which the woven material proved to be more notch sensitive. This implies that the effect of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, adjacent to the 0° plies, in limiting stress relieving mechanisms such as longitudinal splitting, overwhelms any effects due to the distortion of fibre tows in the woven material.

The results of the static tensile tests on the $(0,90,\pm 45)$ lay-up (lay-up D), given in table 4, showed that

the plain woven material was 24% weaker than the non-woven material. This is due to the combination of lower fibre volume fraction and greater fibre distortion, already discussed in connection with lay-up A. Both woven and non-woven material exhibited similar notch sensitivity, as observed in lay-up C, the strength of the woven material being reduced by 22% due to a central 4mm hole and the non-woven material by 26%. However lay-up D was generally stronger than lay-up C, by up to 29%. This difference can be attributed to the different ply stacking sequences, which result in large interlaminar normal stresses at the edges of coupons (7-9) with lay-up C but only small stresses for lay-up D. As a result, longitudinal edge cracks developed in coupons with lay-up C but not lay-up D, and these led to different failure processes and reduced tensile strength.

The tensile strengths of plain (+/-45,0) coupons, (lay-up E), were similar for both non-woven and mixed woven coupons (with only the +/-45° layers replaced by woven fabric), as shown in table 5. This observation has been made in previous work with (+/-45,0) lay-ups (5,6,10,11). A slightly reduced strength would have been expected from the mixed woven coupons because of their lower fibre volume fraction, but this may have been absorbed by the scatter in the results. Both materials were notch sensitive, the non-woven material losing 27% of its strength and the mixed woven 31% due to the action of a 4mm central hole. The degree of notch sensitivity was similar to that observed in lay-ups C and D which also contained +/-45° layers. It is apparent that these layers can seriously limit stress relieving mechanisms such as 0° longitudinal splitting around stress concentrators and lead to high notch sensitivity in composite materials.

Zero-tension fatigue

In the tensile fatigue loading of the (0,90) material (lay-up A), both plain non-woven and woven coupons suffered losses in strength with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles, but the effect was more pronounced in the woven material (fig.1). Thus the static strength difference observed between the non-woven and woven material, due to a combination of lower fibre volume fraction and greater fibre distortion in the woven material, became greater in fatigue loading. Optical microscopy and ultrasonic C-scanning revealed extensive transverse cracks across the 90° layers and delamination between layers, increasing with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles. In the non-woven material this effectively uncoupled the 90° layers from the 0° layers and the behaviour was then typical of unidirectional CFRP in fatigue. In the woven material however, the 90° tows remain interwoven with the 0° tows and thus continue to exert a stress concentrating influence on them. The C-scan revealed areas of damage at tow crossovers, probably involving 0° tow degradation, and this resulted in a steeper S-N curve than observed in the non-woven material.

The strength of the (0,90) holed coupons, both woven and non-woven, increased at first with increasing numbers of fatigue cycles, but fell after greater numbers of cycles (fig.1). The initial increase in strength was only possible

because of the manner in which the fatigue tests were performed, which involved the gradual increase of peak load from zero to maximum over about 20000 fatigue cycles. This was sufficient cyclic loading to develop damage zones around the holes and relieve the stress concentration leading to initially greater strengths. After only 10,000 cycles the holed non-woven coupons were as strong as the plain coupons, but the holed woven coupons never quite attained the strength of the plain coupons, even after 10 million load cycles. Ultrasonic C-scanning revealed the development of longitudinal splitting and 0/90 delamination around the holes, this being the cause of the initial reduction in notch sensitivity. This was more apparent in the non-woven material, explaining why this material recovered more of its plain strength than the woven material. In the holed woven material the 90° tows can never become completely uncoupled from the 0° tows, because of their woven nature, and they continue to exert a stress concentrating influence at the tow crossover points. Indeed these points were the site of additional damage observed experimentally.

The (+/-45) coupons behaved similarly in fatigue, in both the plain and holed state, the notch insensitivity apparent statically being preserved in fatigue. The woven coupons did appear slightly stronger and this became more noticeable at long lifetimes when woven coupons outlasted non-woven ones by almost one decade in life (fig.4). The major microstructural difference observed was less extensive damage in the woven material, presumably a consequence of the damage growth restrictions imposed by the woven nature of the material, and this resulted in survival to longer lifetimes. The woven material also exhibited an overall lightening associated with damage development at tow crossovers, but this did not appear detrimental in the (+/-45) material, unlike other lay-ups.

Tensile fatigue tests on coupons with a (+/-45,0,90) lay-up (lay-up C) showed a substantial loss in strength with increasing numbers of cycles, for both woven and non-woven material (fig.7). Ultrasonic C-scanning and optical microscopy revealed extensive longitudinal edge cracking, growing from the coupon edges towards the centres of their widths, probably the cause of the significant strength losses observed. The plain woven material appeared to suffer an even greater loss in strength at high lifetimes. This implies that the static differences attributed to lower fibre volume fraction and greater fibre distortion in the woven material continued to account for the lower fatigue strength except at long lifetimes when additional strength degradation mechanisms were operative in the woven material. The microstructural analysis again revealed considerable damage at the tow crossover points in the woven material, particularly at long lifetimes, and this undoubtedly resulted in a further reduction in the load bearing capacity of the 0° tows. This caused an additional loss in strength compared with the non-woven material in which the 0° and 90° plies became uncoupled and the stress concentrating effects of the 90° plies on the 0° plies relieved.

The holed woven and non-woven coupons with the (+/-45,0,90) lay-up (lay-up C) also increased in strength initially in the tensile fatigue tests, for the same reason as discussed for lay-up A. Between 100,000 and 1,000,000 cycles

the strengths of the holed coupons approached those of the plain coupons and the notch sensitivity disappeared completely in the non-woven material, but remained to a small extent in the woven material. The C-scan revealed extensive damage growth around holes during fatigue, this linking up with edge cracking caused by the high interlaminar normal stresses in this particular lay-up (7-9). As a consequence, layers became uncoupled, causing considerable stress relief, resulting in the loss of notch sensitivity in the non-woven material. Although the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers can become uncoupled from the $0^\circ, 90^\circ$ layers, leading to stress relaxation, the woven material never became completely notch insensitive as the 0° tows can never become totally uncoupled from the stress concentrating influence of the 90° tows, being intimately woven together. Indeed, woven coupons with the $(0, 90)$ lay-up (lay-up A) remained partially notch sensitive for identical reasons.

Coupons with the $(0, 90, \pm 45)$ lay-up (lay-up D) also showed a significant loss in strength with increasing numbers of tensile fatigue cycles (fig.10). Microstructural analysis revealed less extensive longitudinal edge cracking than in lay-up C, but transverse cracks were formed across the 90° plies and initiated some layer delamination at large numbers of cycles. Considerable damage was also developed in the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers adding to the loss in strength observed. The strength of the woven material remained a similar fraction of that of the non-woven material even up to one million fatigue cycles. This implies that the principal cause for the difference between the strength of the plain woven and non-woven material remained greater fibre distortion and lower fibre volume fraction. This is somewhat surprising since the microstructural analysis revealed, as in coupons with lay-up C, the development of significant damage at the tow crossover points in the woven material after large numbers of fatigue cycles. The effect was most noticeable in lay-up C at lifetimes exceeding one million load cycles, but no coupons with lay-up D survived for longer than one million cycles, simply because of the experimental selection of stress levels. It is possible that a reduction in the strength of the woven material would have been observed at greater numbers of fatigue cycles.

As in lay-up C, the holed non-woven coupons with lay-up D became notch insensitive after about 100,000 load cycles, but the holed woven coupons, although approaching the strength of the plain coupons, never quite became totally notch insensitive. Similar types and degrees of damage were observed around the holes as in coupons with lay-up C, and the main difference between the holed non-woven and woven coupons remained the additional damage developed at tow crossover points in the woven material and the inability of the 90° tows to become completely uncoupled from the 0° tows.

Coupons with lay-up C had greater static strengths than those with lay-up D, but this difference became less obvious during fatigue. This difference was attributed to the extensive longitudinal edge cracking developed in coupons with lay-up C, due to the particular ply stacking sequence, and not observed statically in coupons with lay-up D. The improvement in the fatigue performance of coupons with lay-up C, relative to those with lay-up D, may be because coupons from both lay-ups

developed longitudinal edge cracking in fatigue, although this was always more extensive in coupons with lay-up C.

The static tests on coupons with the (+/-45,0) lay-up (lay-up E) showed there to be little difference in strength between the non-woven and mixed woven coupons, and a similar observation was made in the tensile fatigue tests (fig.12). The plain coupons suffered a loss in strength of nearly 25% after one million load cycles in both the non-woven and mixed woven cases. Previous work had found a greater loss in strength in the non-woven material (10,11), but this was not the case in the present work. Microstructural analysis revealed the damage to be confined mainly to the +/-45° layers, which carry only a small fraction of the applied load. Thus the coupons behaved in a similar manner to unidirectional material, and indeed the loss in strength during fatigue was comparable with that observed in unidirectional material. C-scans of the plain mixed woven coupons did reveal damage at tow crossover points in the +/-45° layers, but since these layers carried only small loads the damage had no significant effect on the material strength.

Tensile fatigue tests on holed coupons with the (+/-45,0) lay-up (lay-up E) showed both the non-woven and mixed woven coupons increased initially in strength, for reasons discussed earlier in this section in connection with coupons with lay-up A. The fatigue strengths of both the non-woven and mixed woven coupons remained similar at all lifetimes and between 100,000 and 1,000,000 cycles the holed coupons became notch insensitive, their strengths matching those of the plain coupons. The ultrasonic C-scan revealed damage development around the holes at low lifetimes, this taking the form of delamination between the +/-45° and 0° layers with longitudinal shear cracks at the edges of the holes. As the tests proceeded, these shear cracks and the associated delamination grew longitudinally towards the coupon ends. The 0° layers thus became uncoupled from the +/-45 layers and behaved in the notch insensitive manner typical of unidirectional material. This behaviour was readily apparent in infra-red thermography studies of the coupons in which the hottest areas were initially either side of the holes but rapidly migrated to above and below the holes and then moved away from the holes towards the coupon ends.

Conclusions

1. When carbon fibre reinforced plastics were made with woven fabric rather than non-woven material, distortion of the load carrying 0° fibres significantly reduced the static tensile strength. When woven fabric was oriented at 45° to the load direction the static tensile strength was similar to or greater than in non-woven +/-45° material.

2. Apart from +/-45° material, which exhibited notch insensitive behaviour, the static tensile strength of all the lay-ups was significantly reduced by the presence of a hole. Replacing just the +/-45° layers of a laminate with woven fabric had little effect on the static tensile strength.

3. In tensile fatigue loading, further significant reductions in strength were observed. In (0,90) and (0,90,+/-45) laminates the poorer performance of the woven material was preserved in fatigue, in both plain and holed cases. Indeed the tow crossover points in the woven material were sites of additional fatigue damage and lead to greater reductions in fatigue strength in many cases. The tensile strength of +/-45 material was also reduced in fatigue loading, although the woven material gave greater fatigue lifetimes than the non-woven material. Thus where +/-45 material is used in isolation, as in many aircraft trailing edge applications, the use of woven fabric will lead to greater fatigue lives. Replacing the +/-45^o layers in 0+/-45 lay-ups with woven fabric had little effect on tensile fatigue behaviour, and could be a useful approach to improving impact resistance without losing tensile strength, statically or in fatigue.

4. In tensile fatigue loading, non-woven holed coupons lost their notch sensitivity after a small number of fatigue cycles. However, because of the additional fatigue degradation processes associated with tow crossover points in the weave, holed woven coupons never quite achieved notch insensitivity in fatigue.

References

1. B.Harris, "Fatigue and accumulation of damage in reinforced plastics," Composites, 8 (4) (1977) pp.214.
2. R.A.Weinberger, A.R.Somoroff, B.L.Riley, "US Navy certification of composite wings for the F-18 and advanced Harrier aircraft," AIAA Journal, 17 (1977) p477.
3. J.C.Watson, "AV-8B composite fuselage design," paper presented at AIAA 19th Aerospace sciences meeting, St.Louis, Mo, January 1981.
4. S.Hanaqud et al, "Comparative evaluation of woven graphite epoxy composites," NASA CR 159001, Georgia Institute of Technology (July 1979).
5. S.M.Bishop and P.T.Curtis, "An assessment of the potential of woven carbon fibre reinforced plastics for aerospace use," Royal Aircraft Establishment Report TR83010, (January 1983).
6. P.T.Curtis and S.M.Bishop, "An assessment of the potential of woven carbon fibre reinforced plastics for high performance applications," Composites, 15 (4) (1984) pp.259-266.
7. P.T.Curtis, "The effect of edge stresses on the failure of (0,45,90) CFRP laminates," Royal Aircraft Establishment report TR80054 (April 1980).
8. P.T.Curtis, "The effect of edge stresses on the failure of (0,45,90) CFRP laminates," Journal of Materials Science, 19 (1984) pp.167-182.
9. P.T.Curtis, "The tensile behaviour of (0,45,90) CFRP laminates - effects of material type and layer thickness,"

Royal Aircraft Establishment Report TR83011 (January 1983).

10.W.Cantwell, P.T.Curtis and J.Morton, "Post-impact fatigue performance of carbon fibre laminates with mixed-woven layers," Composites, 14 (3) (1983) pp.301-306.

11.W.Cantwell, P.T.Curtis and J.Morton, "Impact and subsequent fatigue damage growth in carbon fibre laminates," International Journal of Fatigue, 6 (2) (1984) pp.113-118.